

**PROJECT HOPE (HEALTH OPTIMIZING PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES & EXERCISES)
TOWARDS INCREASING THE FITNESS LEVEL OF
SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of Project HOPE (Health Optimizing Physical Activities & Exercises) towards increasing the fitness level of the Senior High School learners. This study utilized the quasi-experimental research design. A total of 70 learners took part in the study. Paired sample t-test was used to determine whether there was a significant difference in physical fitness test before and after 20 days of the implementation of Project HOPE. The test result revealed that there was a statistically significant improvement on the following areas, BMI ($t(34)=3.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.60$) with 0.60 effect size, 3-minute Step Test: Before ($t(34)=2.58$, $p<0.014$, $d=0.44$) with 0.44 effect size, After ($t(34)=5.81$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.98$) with 0.98 effect size, Strength: Push Up ($t(34)=10.66$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.80$) with 1.80 effect size, Basic Plank ($t(34)=6.83$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.15$) with 1.15 effect size, Flexibility: Zipper test Right ($t(34)=4.96$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.84$) with 0.84 effect size, left ($t(34)=5.84$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.99$) with .99 effect size, Sit and Reach ($t(34)=9.75$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.65$) with 1.65 effect size, Coordination: juggling ($t(34)=9.24$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.56$) with 1.56 effect size, Agility Hexagon ($t(34)=11.58$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.96$) with 1.96 effect size, Speed: 40m ($t(34)=8.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.38$) with 1.38 effect size, Power: Standing long jump ($t(34)=15.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.63$) with 2.63 effect size, Balance: Stork left ($t(34)=11.12$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.88$) with 1.88 effect size, Right ($t(34)=13.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.23$) with 2.23 effect size, and Reaction Time: Stick drop, ($t(34)=12.20$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.06$) with 2.06 effect size. This implies that Project HOPE has a large effect size to the participants. Hence, Project HOPE, as an intervention, helped increase the fitness level of the senior high school learners.

Keywords: *Fitness Level, Health and Skill-Related Fitness, Physical Activities and Exercises, Quasi-Experimental, Senior high School and Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

The primary goal of education has been to develop children's cognitive capacity in the sense of learning academic subjects. This goal establishes a learning atmosphere in which seated learning is regarded as appropriate and successful, as well as rewarded.

Physical education is the only way for all students to learn about physical movement and participate in physical activity as part of their education. As previously stated, its objective and place in formalized education have shifted from teaching cleanliness and health to educating students about the many kinds and advantages of physical activity, such as sports and exercise. With a significant increase of content, physical education has grown into a content area with a variety of learning goals that aid in the overall development of students (NASPE, 2004).

Physical Education promote healthy lifestyle choices that will improve one's quality of life in the future. This means that through physical education, a person can learn enough knowledge and comprehension, exercise abilities, and ideal attitudes to eventually contribute to their well-being. It provides students with movement-based educational experiences that benefit their general health as well as their academic performance and achievement. Physical education activities and sports, according to the Education Commission (2010-2013), contribute not just to physical fitness but also to mental health (Helonde et al., 2018).

As stipulated under Article XIV, Section 19(1) of 1987, the Philippine constitution mandates that the state shall promote Physical Education and encourage sports programs, league competitions and amateur sports including training for international competitions to foster self-discipline, teamwork and excellence for the development of healthy and alert citizenry.

De Leon (1976) stressed that the primordial objective of Physical Education as a venue of moral values and as a workplace for the development of strong and healthy future leaders of tomorrow.

Physical Education is currently a difficult and complex subject to teach. For one thing, educators are concerned not just with developing the capacity of students to attain academic greatness, but also with producing champions of high caliber and emotional intelligence in a variety of sectors both at home and abroad.

Along with the many changes in philosophy and curriculum related to learners and physical education in recent years, there have been some changes in teacher preparation and teacher preparation. A competent elementary and secondary physical education expert emerged from the early years of other less optimal situations.

Background of the Study

Humans' physical activity evolved in tandem with their cultural, emotional, and social evolution. As society became increasingly complicated, leading to the modern age, physical activity became recognized as an organized and controlled form of education, and was named physical education.

The recognition of physical education as an integral element of the basic school curriculum has led to the inevitable conclusion that an untrained individual is simply unfit to lead physical education programs for students.

Physical activity is essential for a healthy lifestyle and has several beneficial effects on the body. Physical inactivity, on the other hand, has a negative impact on body weight and is linked to obesity. Furthermore, exercise is a structured process in which the body and mind are constantly challenged by pressures of varying volumes (quantity) and intensity. Aerobic and anaerobic training are two different types of physical activity. Aerobic exercise, such as aerobics, jogging, swimming, and cycling, makes the heart and lungs work harder to deliver oxygen to the muscles. Lifting weights and running short distances are examples of aerobic exercises that do not require the use of oxygen to replenish fuel. Swimming, for example, is one sport that might help maintain physical fitness.

The fall in adolescent physical activity is linked to adolescents' present low levels of physical fitness and rising obesity rates (Cooper, 2020). Although all five dimensions of physical fitness (body composition, cardiovascular fitness, flexibility, muscular strength, and muscular endurance) are significant, research reveals that certain aspects are more associated with overweight and obesity than others. (Ara et al., 2017). When compared to other physical fitness components like muscular fitness, speed/agility, or flexibility, cardiovascular fitness, for example, has a greater association with overweight and total adiposity.

Rodrigues-Krause et al. (2021) said that dancing has been recommended as a suitable home-based physical activity during the quarantine period associated with the COVID-19 pandemic. Dancing can reduce sedentary behavior and thereby maintain physical and emotional health. This provides support to dance, fitness, and/or other health professionals in guiding individuals wishing to practice dancing activities at home. By considering dancing as a strategy to increase levels of physical activity at home, this is divided into three sections: i) the structure of a dance session, ii) elements of aerobic fitness, and iii) safety considerations. A home setting dance session lasts ~40-50 minutes, including the warm-up, the specific dancing activities, and the cool-down.

Teenagers and adult women are currently favoring Zumba and high-impact aerobics as physical exercises. Aerobic high impact is a type of exercise that combines strength training and stretching to increase all aspects of fitness, including flexibility, muscle strength, and cardiovascular fitness. Aerobic high impact is frequently done in

groups that have been trained with the goal of increasing the intensity of exercise while moving to the beat of faster-paced music.

Zumba is a hybrid of a sports movement and a new dance that incorporates both music and dance. Zumba is also known for being a pleasant way to exercise and for helping to improve cardiovascular fitness. Zumba can also aid in the reduction of skinfold thickness and body mass.

Evidence suggests, however, that increasing physical activity and fitness may improve academic performance, as well as dedicating time in the school day to recess, physical education class, and other physical activities.

Although distance learning for the academic performance stems from a complex interaction between intellect and contextual variables, health is a vital moderating factor in a child's ability to learn. The idea that healthy children learn better is empirically supported and well accepted (Basch, 2018), and multiple studies have confirmed that health benefits are associated with physical activity, including cardiovascular and muscular fitness, bone health, psychosocial occupational, sports, conditioning, domestic, and other activities can all be classified as physical activity in daily life.

Exercise is a type of physical activity that is planned, structured, and repetitive with the goal of improving or maintaining physical fitness as a final or intermediate goal.

Salvatierra (2019) defines fitness as the ability to easily complete daily duties while yet having the stamina to deal with unanticipated emergencies. He went on to say that the more physically active a person is, the more energy he has available throughout the day.

Traditional definitions of physical fitness have included terminology that spans a wide variety of functional abilities when operationalized. These definitions, on the other hand, do not directly allude to the health benefits of physical activity. According to the present state of knowledge in exercise science and society's perception of physical fitness, a definition of physical fitness should emphasize health-related components of fitness. The primary concern of the physical education profession, it is claimed, should be for (NASPE, 2008).

The researcher who is responsible for holistically shaping, it is preferable to have students who are physically, emotionally, cognitively, and spiritually healthy always. The Senior High School learners of San Sebastian Integrated School of Ramon, Isabela, on the other hand, are not doing well.

Thus, Department of Education Order number 34 series 2019 utilized as a basis on their BMI obtained during the Physical Fitness Test, most Senior High School learners are not physically fit, sedentary, or obese. These are some of the reasons the researcher need to act and address the students' needs in order to help them learn and respond more effectively.

This study aimed to determine the effect of the Project HOPE a basis for fitness intervention among senior high school learners of San Sebastian Integrated School.

. As a result, Project HOPE will serve as a wake-up call for them, this project utilize the Pandemic dancing, aerobics, and other forms of exercise can help them increase fitness level, develop and improve their life skills. Paired Sample t-test will be used to determine whether there is a difference in physical fitness test before and after 20 days of the Project HOPE.

Research Questions

1. What is the average fitness level of the control and experiment group before the implementation of the Project HOPE in terms of:

1.1 Health-Related Fitness

1.2 Skill- Related Fitness

2. What is the average fitness level of the control and experiment group after the implementation of the Project HOPE in terms of:

2.1 Health-Related Fitness

2.2 Skill- Related Fitness

3. Is there a significant difference in the fitness level of the senior high school learners before and after the implementation of the Project HOPE.

4. What is the effect size of the Project HOPE intervention in increasing fitness level of the Senior High School learners?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed the the quasi-experimental research design. Quasi-experimental research involves the manipulation of an independent variable without the random assignment of participants to conditions or orders of conditions. Among the important types are non-equivalent groups designs, pretest-posttest, and interrupted time-series designs. The quasi-experimental research is appropriate to assess PROJECT HOPE (Health Optimizing Physical activities & Exercises)

Study Site and Participants

The site of the study in the San Sebastian Integrated School in Ramon, Isabela. San Sebastian Integrated School is an educational institution with a total land area of 10,000 m² designed to provide learning spaces and learning environments in teaching diverse learners. It is one of the integrated schools of Ramon District with a total enrollment of 1051 during the School Year 2021 – 2021 and with 40 permanent teachers and 2 non-teaching personnel with 8 LSB funded teachers and personnel.

San Sebastian Integrated School offers Kindergarten to Grade 12 Program. For Senior High School Department curriculum offering is the General Academic Strand with electives on Beauty Nail Care NCII, Driving NCII and Accountancy Business Management. The Alternative Learning System for Senior High School was recently approved for School Year 2021-2022.

The participants of the study were the senior high school learners enrolled in the second semester of the Academic Year 2021–2022.

Population, Sample Size and Sampling Method

There were seventy (70) senior high school learners attended San Sebastian Integrated School in the Academic Year 2021–2022. With the limited number of participants, the researcher employed total enumeration sampling technique by taking all the senior high school learners as participants of the study. The seventy (70) senior high school learners were divided into two groups. Thirty five (35) learners were selected to composed the control group (no intervention) and thirty-five (35) learners composed the experimental group (with intervention).

Instruments

The primary instrument used in the study was an individual score card adopted from the Deped Order No. 34 series 2019 the Revised Physical Fitness Test developed by Department of Education used to determine the level of health-related and skill-related fitness status of the learners in the various conditions. The performance of the learners were interpreted and leveled in relation to their respective score and points such as excellent, very good, fair, needs improvements and poor.

Data Gathering Procedure

At the start of the study, the researcher sought approval from the Superintendent of the Schools Division to carry out the study. Upon approval, the researcher presented the purpose of the study to the head of the school and requested for their consent to conduct the physical activity exercise to the target participants. To guarantee complete participation, the score sheet was physically sent to each participants. Both groups of participants performed the pre-physical fitness test at the same time and on the same day. Beginning the day after the pre-test, the experimental group engaged themselves in a 1hour physical activities and exercises each morning from 7:00 to 8:00 from Monday to Saturday for a period of 20 days, while the control group carried their routine classroom activities.

Data Analysis

The researcher employed the following statistical tools to analyze and interpret the data gathered:

1. Mean was used to determined the average score of the students on

health-related fitness and skill-related fitness tests;

2. Standard Deviation was used to determine the homogeneity on the responses to the tests;

3. Paired Samples t-test was used to determine the significant difference on the implementation of the Project HOPE

4. Eta² was used to evaluate the effect size of the Project HOPE intervention towards increasing the fitness level of the senior high school learners using the presentation below.

Relative size	Effect size	% of control group below the mean of experimental group
	0.0	50%
Small	0.2	58%
Medium	0.5	69%
Large	0.8	79%
	1.4	92%

RESULTS

Part 1. Average Fitness Level of Control and experiment group before the Implementation of the Project HOPE

Table 1 shows the different test and activities in the revised physical fitness test.

Table 1. Average Fitness Level of Control and Experiment Group before the Implementation of the Project HOPE

TEST	ACTIVITY		CONTROL GROUP		EXPERIMENTAL GROUP	
			AVERAGE	Remarks	AVERAGE	Remarks
PART I Health RELATED FITNESS						
BODY COMPOSITION		BMI	16.44	NORMAL	18.74	NORMAL
CARDIOVASCULAR ENDURANCE	3-minute-step test	Training Heart Rate	107.25	Very Good	119.66	Very Good
		Recovery Heart Rate	70.05	Good	72.91	Good
STRENGTH		Push up	7.10	Fair	6.20	Fair
		Basic plank	3.14	Need Improvement	3.34	Need Improvement
FLEXIBILITY	Zipper test	Right	3.45	Very Good	3.66	Very Good
		Left	3.19	Very Good	3.31	Very Good
	Sit And Reach	Final score	58.67	Very Good	59.89	Very Good
PART II SKILL-RELATED FITNESS						
COORDINATION	JUGGLING		26.50	Good	27.31	Good

AGILITY	HEXAGON		8.03	Excellent	8.60	Excellent
SPEED	40M Run		5.00	Very Good	5.66	Very Good
POWER	Standing long jump		125.25	Good	127.37	Good
BALANCE	STORK BALANCE STAND	Left	126.20	Very Good	127.29	Very Good
		Right	123.30	Very Good	125.51	Very Good
REACTION TIME	STICK DROP		9.03	Very Good	8.66	Very Good

As revealed in Table 1, the average score of the respondents and their Fitness level before the Implementation of the Project HOPE. The BMI Average were 16.44 for control group and for experimental group 18.74 resulted to Normal; Cardiovascular Endurance on 3 –minute step test training heart rate were 107.25 for control group and for experimental group 119.66 resulted to very good and recovery heart rate were 70.05 for control group and for experimental group 72.91 which resulted to Good; Strength on Push Up Test with 7.10 for control group and for experimental group 6.20, fair and Basic Plank with 3.14 for control group and for experimental group 3.34 resulted to need improvement; and Flexibility on Zipper Test Right reached about 3.45 for control group and for experimental group 3.66 and Left about 3.19 for control group and for experimental group 3.31 which both resulted to very good and to Sit and reach with the final score of 58.67 for control group and for experimental group 59.89 resulted to very good.

In addition, coordination doing the juggling 26.50 for control group and for experimental group 27.31 resulted to good, Hexagon for agility 8.03 for control group and for experimental group 8.60 resulted to excellent, 40m run 5.00 for control group and for experimental group 5.66 Very good, standing long jump 125.25 for control group and for experimental group 127.37 resulted to good, for Stork balance stand in left 126.20 for control group and for experimental group 127.29 and in right 123.30 for control group and for experimental group 125.51 resulted to very good and lastly the stick drop measured reaction time 9.03 for control group and for experimental group 8.66 resulted to very good.

Part 2. Average Fitness Level of Control and experiment group after the Implementation of the Project HOPE

Table 2 shows the different test and activities in the revise physical fitness test.

Table 2. Average Fitness Level of Control and Experiment Group after the Implementation of the Project HOPE

TEST	ACTIVITY		CONTROL GROUP		EXPERIMENTAL GROUP	
			AVERAGE	Remarks	AVERAGE	Remarks
PART I Health RELATED FITNESS						
BODY COMPOSITION		BMI	17.30	NORMAL	20.34	NORMAL
CARDIOVASCULAR	3-minute-step test	Training Heart Rate	108.05	Very Good	125.83	Excellent

ENDURANCE		Recovery Heart Rate	71.10	Good	81.66	Good
STRENGTH		Push up	10.35	Fair	11.63	Fair
		Basic plank	3.19	Need Improvement	5.54	Need Improvement
FLEXIBILITY	Zipper test	Right	3.58	Very Good	4.40	Excellent
		Left	3.40	Very Good	4.29	Excellent
	Sit And Reach	Final score	65.80	Very Good	76.74	Excellent
PART II SKILL-RELATED FITNESS						
COORDINATION	JUGGLING		27.40	Good	34.00	Very Good
AGILITY	HEXAGON		8.10	Excellent	5.80	Excellent
SPEED	40M Run		4.50	Very Good	4.46	Excellent
POWER	Standing long jump		148.15	Good	167.03	Very Good
BALANCE	STORK BALANCE STAND	Left	126.80	Very Good	167.23	Excellent
		Right	125.10	Very Good	166.34	Excellent
REACTION TIME	STICK DROP		8.30	Very Good	5.66	Very Good

As presented in Table 2, the average score of the respondents and their Fitness level after the Implementation of the Project HOPE. The BMI Average were 17.30 for control group and for experimental group 20.34 resulted to Normal; Cardiovascular Endurance on 3 –minute step test training heart rate were 108.05 for control group and for experimental group 125.83 resulted to excellent and recovery heart rate were 71.10 for control group and for experimental group 81.66 which resulted to Good; Strength on Push Up Test with 10.35 for control group and for experimental group 11.63 , fair and Basic Plank with 3.19 for control group and for experimental group 5.54 resulted to need improvement; and Flexibility on Zipper Test Right reached about 3.58 for control group and for experimental group 4.40 and Left about 3.40 for control group and for experimental group 4.29 which both resulted to excellent and to Sit and reach with the final score of 65.80 for control group and for experimental group 76.74 resulted to excellent.

In the skill-related fitness, coordination doing the juggling 27.40 for control group and for experimental group 34.00 resulted to very good, Hexagon for agility 5.60 resulted to excellent, 40m run 8.10 for control group and for experimental group 4.46 excellent, standing long jump 148.15 for control group and for experimental group 167.07 resulted to very good for Stork balance stand in left 126.80 for control group and for experimental group 167.23 and in right 125.10 for control group and for experimental group 166.341 resulted to both excellent and lastly the stick drop measured reaction time 8.30 for control group and for experimental group 5.66 resulted to very good.

Part 3. Difference Between Pre-test and Posttest after the Implementation of the Project HOPE

Table 3 shows the Paired Sample t-test used to determine whether there was a significant difference in physical fitness test before and after 20 days of implementation of Project HOPE.

Table 3. Significant Difference between Pre-test and Post-test after the Implementation of the Project HOPE

BODY COMPOSITION		N	M	SD	t	df	p-value
BMI	Pre-Test	35	18.74	3.43	3.55	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	20.34	2.40			
CARDIOVASCULAR ENDURANCE							
3-MINUTE STEP TEST							
BEFORE	Pre-Test	35	119.66	23.61	2.58	34	.014
	Post-Test	35	125.83	25.72			
AFTER	Pre-Test	35	72.91	24.04	5.81	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	81.66	19.04			
STRENGTH							
PUSH UP	Pre-Test	35	6.20	3.34	10.66	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	11.63	4.56			
BASIC PLANK	Pre-Test	35	3.34	1.08	6.83	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	5.54	1.44			
FLEXIBILITY							
ZIPPER TEST							
RIGHT	Pre-Test	35	3.66	0.97	4.96	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	4.40	0.60			
LEFT	Pre-Test	35	3.31	0.96	5.84	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	4.29	0.62			
SIT AND REACH							
FINAL	Pre-Test	35	59.89	19.68	9.75	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	76.74	12.54			
COORDINATION							
JUGGLING	Pre-Test	35	27.31	3.39	9.24	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	34.00	4.54			
AGILITY							
HEXAGON	Pre-Test	35	8.60	1.65	11.58	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	5.80	0.83			
SPEED							
40M	Pre-Test	35	5.66	0.94	8.18	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	4.46	0.61			
POWER							
SLJ	Pre-Test	35	127.37	10.72	15.55	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	167.03	12.55			
BALANCE STORK							
LEFT	Pre-Test	35	127.29	13.91	11.12	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	165.23	14.74			
RIGHT	Pre-Test	35	125.51	13.44	13.18	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	166.34	12.27			
REACTION TIME							

STICK DROP	Pre-Test	35	8.66	1.94	12.20	34	.001
	Post-Test	35	5.66	1.03			

As gleaned in Table 3, the result revealed that there was a statistically significant improvement on the following areas, BMI ($t(34)=3.55$, $p<0.001$), 3-minute Step Test: Before ($t(34)=2.58$, $p<0.014$), After ($t(34)=5.81$, $p<0.001$), Strength: Push Up ($t(34)=10.66$, $p<0.001$), Basic Plank ($t(34)=6.83$, $p<0.001$), Flexibility: Zipper test Right ($t(34)=4.96$, $p<0.001$), left ($t(34)=5.84$, $p<0.001$), Sit and Reach ($t(34)=9.75$, $p<0.001$), Coordination: juggling ($t(34)=9.24$, $p<0.001$), Agility Hexagon ($t(34)=11.58$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.96$), Speed: 40m ($t(34)=8.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.38$), Power: Standing long jump ($t(34)=15.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.63$), Balance: Stork left ($t(34)=11.12$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.88$), Right ($t(34)=13.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.23$), and Reaction Time: Stick drop, ($t(34)=12.20$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.06$).

Part 4. The Effect size of Project HOPE

Table 4 shows the effect size of Project HOPE

Table 4. The Effect size of Project HOPE

BODY COMPOSITION		N	M	SD	t	df	p-value	Effect Size
BMI	Pre-Test	35	18.74	3.43	3.55	34	.001	0.60
	Post-Test	35	20.34	2.40				
CARDIOVASCULAR ENDURANCE								
3-MINUTE STEP TEST								
BEFORE	Pre-Test	35	119.66	23.61	2.58	34	.014	0.44
	Post-Test	35	125.83	25.72				
AFTER	Pre-Test	35	72.91	24.04	5.81	34	.001	0.98
	Post-Test	35	81.66	19.04				
STRENGTH								
PUSH UP	Pre-Test	35	6.20	3.34	10.66	34	.001	1.80
	Post-Test	35	11.63	4.56				
BASIC PLANK	Pre-Test	35	3.34	1.08	6.83	34	.001	1.15
	Post-Test	35	5.54	1.44				
FLEXIBILITY								
ZIPPER TEST								
RIGHT	Pre-Test	35	3.66	0.97	4.96	34	.001	0.84
	Post-Test	35	4.40	0.60				
LEFT	Pre-Test	35	3.31	0.96	5.84	34	.001	0.99
	Post-Test	35	4.29	0.62				
SIT AND REACH								
FINAL	Pre-Test	35	59.89	19.68	9.75	34	.001	1.65
	Post-Test	35	76.74	12.54				
COORDINATION								
JUGGLING	Pre-Test	35	27.31	3.39	9.24	34	.001	1.56
	Post-Test	35	34.00	4.54				
AGILITY								
HEXAGON	Pre-Test	35	8.60	1.65		34	.001	1.96

	Post-Test	35	5.80	0.83	11.58			
SPEED								
40M	Pre-Test	35	5.66	0.94	8.18	34	.001	1.38
	Post-Test	35	4.46	0.61				
POWER								
SLJ	Pre-Test	35	127.37	10.72	15.55	34	.001	2.63
	Post-Test	35	167.03	12.55				
BALANCE								
STORK								
LEFT	Pre-Test	35	127.29	13.91	11.12	34	.001	1.88
	Post-Test	35	165.23	14.74				
RIGHT	Pre-Test	35	125.51	13.44	13.18	34	.001	2.23
	Post-Test	35	166.34	12.27				
REACTION TIME								
STICK DROP	Pre-Test	35	8.66	1.94	12.20	34	.001	2.06
	Post-Test	35	5.66	1.03				

As revealed in Table 4 the effect size to the respondents on the following areas, BMI ($t(34)=3.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.60$) with 0.60 effect size, 3-minute Step Test: Before ($t(34)=2.58$, $p<0.014$, $d=0.44$) with 0.44 effect size, After ($t(34)=5.81$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.98$) with 0.98 effect size, Strength: Push Up ($t(34)=10.66$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.80$) with 1.80 effect size, Basic Plank ($t(34)=6.83$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.15$) with 1.15 effect size, Flexibility: Zipper test Right ($t(34)=4.96$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.84$) with 0.84 effect size, left ($t(34)=5.84$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.99$) with .99 effect size, Sit and Reach ($t(34)=9.75$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.65$) with 1.65 effect size, Coordination: juggling ($t(34)=9.24$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.56$) with 1.56 effect size, Agility Hexagon ($t(34)=11.58$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.96$) with 1.96 effect size, Speed: 40m ($t(34)=8.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.38$) with 1.38 effect size, Power: Standing long jump ($t(34)=15.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.63$) with 2.63 effect size, Balance: Stork left ($t(34)=11.12$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.88$) with 1.88 effect size, Right ($t(34)=13.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.23$) with 2.23 effect size, and Reaction Time: Stick drop, ($t(34)=12.20$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.06$) with 2.06 effect size. This implies that Project HOPE has a large effect size to the participants. Hence, Project HOPE, as an intervention, helped increase the fitness level of the senior high school learners.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to determine the effect of Project HOPE (Health Optimizing Physical activities & Exercises) towards increasing the fitness level of senior high school learner.

The average score of the senior high school learners in their fitness level before the implementation of the Project HOPE were the following: The Body Mass Index (BMI) Average were 16.44 for the control group and 18.74 for the experimental group that resulted to Normal; Cardiovascular Endurance on 3 –minute step test training heart rate were 107.25 for the control group and 119.66 for the experimental group that resulted to

very good and recovery heart rate were 70.05 for the control group and 72.91 for that experimental group that resulted to Good; Strength on Push Up Test with 7.10 for the control group and 6.20 for the experimental group, fair and Basic Plank with 3.14 for the control group and 3.34 for the experimental group that resulted to need improvement; and Flexibility on Zipper Test Right reached about 3.45 for the control group and 3.66 for the experimental group and Left about 3.19 for the control group and 3.31 for the experimental group which both resulted to very good and to Sit and reach with the final score of 58.67 for the control group and 59.89 for the experimental group that resulted to very good.

In addition, coordination doing the juggling 26.50 for the control group and 27.31 for the experimental group that resulted to good, Hexagon for agility 8.03 for the control group and 8.60 for the experimental group that resulted to excellent, 40m run 5.00 for the control group and 5.66 for the experimental group that resulted to very good, standing long jump 125.25 for the control group and 127.37 for the experimental group that resulted to good, for Stork balance stand in left 126.20 for the control group and 127.29 for the experimental group and in right 123.30 for the control group and 125.51 for the experimental group that resulted to very good and lastly the stick drop measured reaction time 9.03 for the control group and 8.66 for the experimental group that resulted to very good.

Linda and Banville (2016) indicated student preference for a wider variety in sport and fitness activities, an increase in level of challenge in physical education classes, and an increase in student motivation for participating in activities outside of school.

The average score of the senior high school learners in their fitness level after the implementation of the Project HOPE were the following: The Body Mass Index (BMI) Average were 17.30 for the control group and 20.34 for the experimental group that resulted to Normal; Cardiovascular Endurance on 3-minute step test training heart rate were 108.05 for the control group and 125.83 for the experimental group that resulted to excellent and recovery heart rate were 71.10 for the control group and 81.66 for the experimental group that resulted to Good; Strength on Push Up Test with 10.35 for the control group and 11.63 for the experimental group, fair and Basic Plank with 3.19 for the control group and 5.54 for the experimental group that resulted to need improvement; and Flexibility on Zipper Test Right reached about 3.58 for the control group and 4.40 for the experimental group and Left about 3.40 for the control group and 4.29 for the experimental group which both resulted to excellent and to Sit and reach with the final score of 65.80 for the control group and 76.74 for the experimental group that resulted to excellent.

In the skill-related fitness, coordination doing the juggling 27.40 for the control group and 34.00 for the experimental group that resulted to very good, Hexagon for agility 5.60 that resulted to excellent, 40m run 8.10 for the control group and 4.46 for the experimental group excellent, standing long jump 148.15 for the control group and 167.07 for the experimental group that resulted to very good for Stork balance stand in left 126.80 for the control group and 167.23 for the experimental group and in right 125.10

for the control group and 166.341 for the experimental group that resulted to both excellent and lastly the stick drop measured reaction time 8.30 for the control group and 5.66 for experimental group that resulted to very good.

Goldfine and Nahas (2019) posted ascertained effects of exposing high school students to classroom health-related fitness instruction involving a curriculum focused on the exercise to cardiorespiratory fitness, body composition, flexibility, strength (particularly as it relates to abdominal and lower-back musculoskeletal function), and muscular endurance.

Significant Difference between Pre-test and Post-test after the Implementation of the Project HOPE, the test result revealed that there was a statistically significant improvement on the following areas, BMI ($t(34)=3.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.60$), 3-minute Step Test: Before ($t(34)=2.58$, $p<0.014$, $d=0.44$), After ($t(34)=5.81$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.98$), Strength: Push Up ($t(34)=10.66$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.80$), Basic Plank ($t(34)=6.83$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.15$), Flexibility: Zipper test Right ($t(34)=4.96$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.84$), left ($t(34)=5.84$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.99$), Sit and Reach ($t(34)=9.75$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.65$), Coordination: juggling ($t(34)=9.24$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.56$), Agility Hexagon ($t(34)=11.58$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.96$), Speed: 40m ($t(34)=8.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.38$), Power: Standing long jump ($t(34)=15.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.63$), Balance: Stork left ($t(34)=11.12$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.88$), Right ($t(34)=13.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.23$), and Reaction Time: Stick drop, ($t(34)=12.20$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.06$).

Pesce, et al.,(2021) findings that significant increase in the children's fitness level were motor competence, enjoyment and the amount of Physical activities.

The Effect size of the Project HOPE to the senior high school learners were the following areas, BMI ($t(34)=3.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.60$) with 0.60 effect size, 3-minute Step Test: Before ($t(34)=2.58$, $p<0.014$, $d=0.44$) with 0.44 effect size, After ($t(34)=5.81$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.98$) with 0.98 effect size, Strength: Push Up ($t(34)=10.66$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.80$) with 1.80 effect size, Basic Plank ($t(34)=6.83$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.15$) with 1.15 effect size, Flexibility: Zipper test Right ($t(34)=4.96$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.84$) with 0.84 effect size, left ($t(34)=5.84$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.99$) with .99 effect size, Sit and Reach ($t(34)=9.75$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.65$) with 1.65 effect size, Coordination: juggling ($t(34)=9.24$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.56$) with 1.56 effect size, Agility Hexagon ($t(34)=11.58$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.96$) with 1.96 effect size, Speed: 40m ($t(34)=8.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.38$) with 1.38 effect size, Power: Standing long jump ($t(34)=15.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.63$) with 2.63 effect size, Balance: Stork left ($t(34)=11.12$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.88$) with 1.88 effect size, Right ($t(34)=13.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.23$) with 2.23 effect size, and Reaction Time: Stick drop, ($t(34)=12.20$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.06$) with 2.06 effect size.

Demetriou and Höner (2021) concluded that Numerous school-based physical activity interventions achieved positive effects.

Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, the researcher presented the following conclusions:

1. Average Fitness Level of Control and Experiment Group before the Implementation of the Project HOPE. The BMI Average were 16.44 for control group and for experimental group 18.74 resulted to Normal; Cardiovascular Endurance on 3 minute step test training heart rate were 107.25 for control group and for experimental group 119.66 resulted to very good and recovery heart rate were 70.05 for control group and for experimental group 72.91 which resulted to Good; Strength on Push Up Test with 7.10 for control group and for experimental group 6.20, fair and Basic Plank with 3.14 for control group and for experimental group 3.34 resulted to need improvement; and Flexibility on Zipper Test Right reached about 3.45 for control group and for experimental group 3.66 and Left about 3.19 for control group and for experimental group 3.31 which both resulted to very good and to Sit and reach with the final score of 58.67 for control group and for experimental group 59.89 resulted to very good.

In addition, coordination doing the juggling 26.50 for control group and for experimental group 27.31 resulted to good, Hexagon for agility 8.03 for control group and for experimental group 8.60 resulted to excellent, 40m run 5.00 for control group and for experimental group 5.66 Very good, standing long jump 125.25 for control group and for experimental group 127.37 resulted to good, for Stork balance stand in left 126.20 for control group and for experimental group 127.29 and in right 123.30 for control group and for experimental group 125.51 resulted to very good and lastly the stick drop measured reaction time 9.03 for control group and for experimental group 8.66 resulted to very good.

2. Average Fitness Level of Control and Experiment Group after the Implementation of the Project HOPE. The BMI Average were 17.30 for control group and for experimental group 20.34 resulted to Normal; Cardiovascular Endurance on 3 minutes step test training heart rate were 108.05 for control group and for experimental group 125.83 resulted to excellent and recovery heart rate were 71.10 for control group and for experimental group 81.66 which resulted to Good; Strength on Push Up Test with 10.35 for control group and for experimental group 11.63, fair and Basic Plank with 3.19 for control group and for experimental group 5.54 resulted to need improvement; and Flexibility on Zipper Test Right reached about 3.58 for control group and for experimental group 4.40 and Left about 3.40 for control group and for experimental group 4.29 which both resulted to excellent and to Sit and reach with the final score of 65.80 for control group and for experimental group 76.74 resulted to excellent.

In the skill-related fitness, coordination doing the juggling 27.40 for control group and for experimental group 34.00 resulted to very good, Hexagon for agility 5.60 resulted to excellent, 40m run 8.10 for control group and for experimental group 4.46 excellent, standing long jump 148.15 for control group and for experimental group 167.07 resulted to very good for Stork balance stand in left 126.80 for control group and for experimental group 167.23 and in right 125.10 for control group and for experimental group 166.341

resulted to both excellent and lastly the stick drop measured reaction time 8.30 for control group and for experimental group 5.66 resulted to very good.

3. Significant Difference between Pre-test and Post-test after the Implementation of the Project HOPE. There was a statistically significant improvement on the following areas, BMI ($t(34)=3.55$, $p<0.001$), 3-minute Step Test: Before ($t(34)=2.58$, $p<0.014$), After ($t(34)=5.81$, $p<0.001$), Strength: Push Up ($t(34)=10.66$, $p<0.001$), Basic Plank ($t(34)=6.83$, $p<0.001$), Flexibility: Zipper test Right ($t(34)=4.96$, $p<0.001$), left ($t(34)=5.84$, $p<0.001$), Sit and Reach ($t(34)=9.75$, $p<0.001$), Coordination: juggling ($t(34)=9.24$, $p<0.001$), Agility Hexagon ($t(34)=11.58$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.96$), Speed: 40m ($t(34)=8.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.38$), Power: Standing long jump ($t(34)=15.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.63$), Balance: Stork left ($t(34)=11.12$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.88$), Right ($t(34)=13.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.23$), and Reaction Time: Stick drop, ($t(34)=12.20$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.06$)

4. The Effect size of Project HOPE. the effect size to the respondents on the following areas, BMI ($t(34)=3.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.60$) with 0.60 effect size, 3-minute Step Test: Before ($t(34)=2.58$, $p<0.014$, $d=0.44$) with 0.44 effect size, After ($t(34)=5.81$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.98$) with 0.98 effect size, Strength: Push Up ($t(34)=10.66$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.80$) with 1.80 effect size, Basic Plank ($t(34)=6.83$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.15$) with 1.15 effect size, Flexibility: Zipper test Right ($t(34)=4.96$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.84$) with 0.84 effect size, left ($t(34)=5.84$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.99$) with .99 effect size, Sit and Reach ($t(34)=9.75$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.65$) with 1.65 effect size, Coordination: juggling ($t(34)=9.24$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.56$) with 1.56 effect size, Agility Hexagon ($t(34)=11.58$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.96$) with 1.96 effect size, Speed: 40m ($t(34)=8.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.38$) with 1.38 effect size, Power: Standing long jump ($t(34)=15.55$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.63$) with 2.63 effect size, Balance: Stork left ($t(34)=11.12$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.88$) with 1.88 effect size, Right ($t(34)=13.18$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.23$) with 2.23 effect size, and Reaction Time: Stick drop, ($t(34)=12.20$, $p<0.001$, $d=2.06$) with 2.06 effect size. This implies that Project HOPE has a large effect size to the participants. Hence, Project HOPE, as an intervention, helped increase the fitness level of the senior high school learners.

Recommendations

In the light of the aforementioned conclusion, the researcher recommends the following:

1. Senior high school learners are encouraged to participate religiously in the Project HOPE intervention
2. Teachers are encouraged to give recognition to those senior high school learners who displayed active participation in the Project HOPE intervention
3. Senior high school learners should create a balance between academic and physical activities. However, more attention should be directed to physical activities and exercises that has something to do in the increasing the fitness level to maintain body physique.

School Administrators and teachers should disseminate clearly the Project HOPE intervention to be undertaken for effective participation of the senior high school learners

Similar studies should be conducted by other researchers utilizing other variables not covered in the present that would help increase the fitness level of the learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To meet the ethical consideration of the study, the researcher complied with the ethical and legal requirements related to the conduct of the study. The parents of the participants were notified and signed the informed consent form that include their decision in case they decided to withdraw or discontinue their participation from the study anytime, not expose them to any pressure or harm, kept their anonymity where no one will have access to the information about them and much more be disclosed with others.

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